

IoT based Remote Patient Monitoring System

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Abstract – Remote monitoring system using IoT has higher advantages over patient's health monitoring system. The patient's health is monitored by setting the sensor in the room or by wearing the sensors with the body. These sensors are connected together forming the wireless sensor network which is connected to cloud or Internet. Such networked sensors called IoT is used to make possible gathering of rich information indicative of physical, mental health and behavior of patient. IoT make use of medical equipments more productive by allowing real time monitoring of patient health, in which sensor acquire data of patient's and decreases the human error. The captured data on a continual basis are aggregated and effectively mined to bring out the health and behavioral aspects of patient. There are various frame work like KIT, IOIO-OTG etc, through which the health information of patients is gathered, monitored and analyzed. In this paper, the use of IoT in healthcare system and challenges of IoT in healthcare system are reviewed..

Keywords: Remote Patient Monitoring System, IoT, Raspberry Pi

I. Introduction

The erratic growth of the “Internet of Things” is leading the world is allowing public to initiate new designs and products at home. IoT is used in monitoring patient's health, for making a smart hospitalization and a smart city. The surprised highs and lows of the healthcare parameters such as body temperature, respiration rate, heartbeat, body movement etc of a patient are monitored using sensors of IoT. One of the recent platforms for implementing IoT for remote patient monitoring system (RPMS) is the Raspberry Pi because it offers a whole Linux server in a very small platform at a very low cost. The combination of Raspberry Pi and IoT becomes a new innovation and efficient technology in healthcare system. Raspberry Pi actually bridges as a small clinic after connecting sensors. Raspberry Pi collects the raw data of patient's and the data from sensors are then transferred to Cloud or Internet.

II. Remote Patient Monitoring System

The framework for remote patient monitoring system (RPMS) uses three layer architecture: Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN), Communication and networking layer, Service management layer. The WBAN consists one or more end-system-Transceiver (EST). Each EST consists of wearable sensors as data acquisition unit and transceiver. The communication and networking layer consists of one or more gateway transceiver (GT) which is responsible for collecting and aggregating the data from end-system. The aggregated data is sent to cloud or internet. A set of EST is associated with a GT in the communication and network layer. The service management layer is provides the services such giving suggestion to patient, informing alert message to care-taker. For example a EST measures

various physiological parameters such as blood pressure and body temperature from the wearable sensors and transmit the gathered information to a gateway transceiver through Bluetooth connection. The gateway transceiver turns the data into an Observation and Measurement file and stores it on a remote server for later retrieval by clinicians through the Internet. A cloud based medical data storage system provides access to medical staff through content service application.

Dohr et al [1] monitors blood pressure level using Keep In Touch (KIT) and closed loop healthcare services. Keep In Touch (KIT) uses smart objects and technologies (Near Field Communication and Radio Frequency Identification) to facilitate telemonitoring processes. Closed Loop Healthcare Services take use of KIT technology and are capable of processing relevant data and establishing communication channels between elderly people and their environment and different groups of care-givers (physicians, relatives, mobile care providers). The combination of KIT technology (smart objects) and Closed Loop Healthcare Services results in an applied IoT infrastructure. Through the combination of KIT and Closed Loop Healthcare, a Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) paradigm can be realized through the IoT, where the elderly live in their homes with smart objects, thus smart homes, communicating to the outside world in an intelligent and goal-orientated manner. Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) encompasses technical systems to support elderly people in their daily routine to allow an independent and safe lifestyle as long as possible. In KIT method, JAVA based mobile phone is connected to the KIT with the help of near field communication. After touching the KIT, the data is sent to mobile phone connected to the KIT. In closed loop services, the raw data is gathering from mobile phone and sent to Internet. Those who are associated with patient can monitor patient's blood pressure level.

Junaid mohammed et al [2] monitors patient's ECG wave anywhere in the world using IOIO- OTG Microcontroller which is connected to an android phone using Bluetooth or USB cable. The collected data from the patient is sent to android application. Mohammed S. Jasses et al [3] focused on monitoring and analyzing body temperature of patient from the stored data available with cloud. The sensors connected with Raspberry pi in turn sends the sensed data to cloud. Hasmah Mansor et al [4] discussed on monitoring body temperature using LM35 temperature sensor. The LM35 temperature sensor is interfaced to the Arduino uno board which in turn sends the data to Internet for access by others. Mathan Kumar et al [6] proposed RPMS for monitoring ECG, Respiration rate, heart rate and body temperature using the sensors connected with PIC16F887A microcontroller. Karandeep Malhi et al [7] discussed on monitoring body temperature, heart rate using C8051F020 microcontroller. Wearable sensors on patients are used to collect data and then sent to micro controller. Zigbee module is initially interface to this microcontroller and then that module transfers or communicates data to the nearest receiver.

Nithin P. Jain et al [8] discussed on monitoring temperature, bloodpressure, heart rate of patient. Microcontroller AT Mega 32 is used for interfacing these sensors with their general purpose pins. GSM module is also interfaced to this microcontroller. After collecting data, SMS is sent to the doctor based on the condition of the patient. Soumya Roy et al [9] discussed on monitoring ECG waves of patient's. AT Mega 16L microcontroller is used in this paper for monitoring ECG waves. Zigbee module is used for analysing ECG waves. Zigbee module sends data to nearest connected system or receiver. Alessandro De Gloria et al [10] discuss on two important issues: (i) paving way for an easier interface of wireless sensors and embedded devices using heterogeneous link layer technologies using dedicated protocols (e.g., 6LowPan, CoAP, etc.); and (ii) recognizing a service-oriented architecture and averaging the merging towards the Web of Things (WoT)

III. Methodology

Fig 1 shows the block the diagram of patient monitoring system using Raspberry Pi. The wearable sensor device monitors the health of patient regularly. The wearable sensor device consists of temperature and pulse rate sensor to keep a regular track of health variations in body temperature, body movements of patient and heart rate of the patients. These sensors signals are sent to the Raspberry Pi, It sends all the current health data of the particular patient to the Internet for access by any person related to the patient.

Fig 1 Block diagram of Patient Monitoring system using Raspberry Pi

IV. Discussion

In addition to the technology for data gathering, storage and access, medical data analysis and visualization are critical components of remote health monitoring systems. Accurate diagnoses and monitoring of patient's medical condition relies on analysis of medical records containing various physiological characteristics over a long period of time. Dealing with data of high dimensionality in both time and quantity makes data analysis task quite frustrating and error prone for clinicians. Although the use of data mining and visualization techniques had previously been addressed as a solution to the aforementioned challenge, these methods have only recently gained attention in remote health monitoring systems. While the advent of electronic remote health monitoring systems has promised to revolutionize the conventional health care methods, integrating the IoT paradigm into these systems can further increase intelligence, flexibility and interoperability. A device utilizing the IoT scheme is uniquely addressed and identifiable at any time and anywhere through the Internet. IoT based devices in remote health monitoring systems are not only capable of the conventional sensing tasks but can also exchange information with each other, automatically connect to and exchange information with health institutes through the Internet, significantly simplifying set up and administration tasks. Such systems are able to provide services such as automatic alarm to the nearest healthcare institute in the event of a critical accident for a supervised patient.

V. Conclusion

A large amount of data is collected using the Remote Patient Monitoring System. This colossal amount of data, consisting medical history of many patients' parameters and corresponding results, can be explored using signal

processing techniques and data mining, in search of consistent patterns and systematic relationships in the disease. This could be a point of paramount significance for the medical research. Simply, the researchers provided with actual results which make their study easier. Additionally, they can also predict the nature of disease and take some preventive measures in advance. For instance, if a patient's health parameters are changing in the same pattern as those of a previous patient in the database, the consequences can also be estimated. If the same patterns are repeatedly confirmed, it would be easier for the remedy.

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